

Whole-genome sequencing data of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* isolates obtained from Latvian patients with tuberculosis

Version 0

Description

This DMP applies to raw whole-genome sequencing data of *M. tuberculosis* isolates obtained from Latvian patients diagnosed with pulmonary or extrapulmonary tuberculosis, some of whom experienced recurrent tuberculosis episodes or were involved in local transmission chains.

Funder

Central Finance and
Contracting Agency

Grant

Consolidation of the Latvian
Institute of Organic Synthesis
and the Latvian Biomedical
Research and Study Centre
(5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/001)

Researchers

Darja Sadovska (orcid:0000-0002-2902-9267)

Organizations

Latvian Biomedical Research and Study Centre

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Whole-genome sequencing data of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* isolates obtained from Latvian patients with tuberculosis

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Central Finance and Contracting Agency

Grants: Consolidation of the Latvian Institute of Organic Synthesis and the Latvian Biomedical Research and Study Centre (5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/001)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2024-10-01

4. Templates

Descriptions

Tracing the source of infection for the paediatric tuberculosis patient

This dataset involves 11 *M. tuberculosis* isolates obtained from eight patients with tuberculosis, including one paediatric patient. All isolates represented one active tuberculosis episode, except for one case of a single prolonged episode; one patient had three episodes. Epidemiological links were established between all patients.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The data collection includes raw whole-genome sequencing data of *M. tuberculosis* isolates obtained from epidemiologically linked patients with tuberculosis. The acquired sequencing data were used for mycobacterial strain genotyping, genotypic drug susceptibility testing, delineation of transmission chains, and determination of causes of recurrent tuberculosis episodes, consistently aligning with the project's objective of advancing knowledge on tuberculosis transmission and recurrence.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

FASTQ

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

8

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Re-use of existing data is not planned for the current research.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data may be useful to other researchers studying the epidemiological aspects of tuberculosis.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence (MIxS)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The sequencing data will be made publicly available upon submission of the manuscript, which describes the analysis of this dataset, to an open-access journal.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

European Nucleotide Archive

European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) specialises in managing and sharing nucleotide sequence data, including raw and processed sequencing data, making it ideal for whole-genome sequencing data of *M. tuberculosis*. ENA's robust infrastructure supports comprehensive data management and ensures broad accessibility and interoperability with other bioinformatics resources. ENA's submission guidelines have been reviewed and generated data and metadata will comply with their requirements.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The standard bioinformatic software tools are typically required to access and analyse the sequencing data in FASTQ format. The pipeline can vary depending on the objective of the analysis.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The FASTQ format is an open, text-based format widely supported by various bioinformatics tools. It is designed for easy integration and recombination with other datasets, allowing seamless use in different software applications and workflows.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

NCBI Taxonomy

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy>

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

This license allows others to share and adapt the data for any purpose, being the most permissive and enabling the widest possible re-use.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2024-12-30

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2034-12-30

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

The dataset provided consists of raw sequencing data. Quality assurance for raw sequencing data is typically handled through the standard analysis pipeline used to process the data. While specific quality parameters or additional quality control measures are not included in this upload, users are encouraged to perform quality assessments using tools like FastQC to evaluate the data as needed.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

The costs for making the data FAIR during the project will be covered within the framework of the European Union's Recovery and Resilience Mechanism project No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/001 "Consolidation of the Latvian Institute of Organic Synthesis and the Latvian Biomedical Research and Study Centre".

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Darja Sadovska (orcid: [0000-0002-2902-9267](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2902-9267))

The person responsible for data management will oversee the organisation, documentation, and distribution of the data, ensuring it is accessible, properly archived, and compliant with relevant standards and protocols.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Costs for maintaining and ensuring the data remains FAIR after project realisation will be supported by ongoing funding or institutional resources allocated for data management and preservation.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Passwords

Passwords will be used to set up password-protected access to data storage systems and files, ensuring that only authorised users can access and manage the sequencing data before it is uploaded to the repository. Once uploaded, ENA will handle data security and encryption on its servers.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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